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Interdisciplinary project-led engineering education The coaching role of the tutor

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ABSTRACT

Professionals are increasingly expected to collaborate in interdisciplinary settings. Higher education institutes offer students opportunities to develop necessary skills, often in the context of project-led education. In such types of education, the role of the tutor is changing, from a focus on teacher-oriented teaching towards learner-oriented coaching, facilitating students' knowledge construction. Hardly any research focuses on how teachers apply this new didactical approach and how it impacts student learning.

In our research, we study how tutors in interdisciplinary engineering education take on the coaching role and how tutors and students value this coaching behavior as beneficial for student learning.

Context is the interdisciplinary semester in Saxion University of Applied Sciences, where third-year bachelor students from three or more (engineering) disciplines work together in project teams on large (25 ECTS) projects, provided by research groups and business partners.

Ten tutors were filmed during a one-hour tutoring session. From each film, six fragments were selected as input for semi-structured interviews fostering reflection with the tutor and with students. The results were connected to teacher beliefs and to students' evaluation and interpretation of the tutor behavior. Results are presented with respect to interdisciplinarity, and to tutoring behavior, and how students appreciate it.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Professionals are increasingly expected to collaborate in interdisciplinary settings. Higher education institutes offer students opportunities to develop necessary skills, through project-led education, offering contexts in which teachers and workforce professionals may have a shared responsibility for student learning. Such 'hybrid learning configurations' can be defined as "*a social practice around ill-defined, authentic tasks or issues whose resolution requires transboundary learning (e.g. by transcending disciplines, traditional structures and sectors, and forms of learning)*" [1 pp. 310]. While researching and solving the challenges posed, students -as future professionals- develop competencies and attitudes, such as being inquisitive, entrepreneurial, adaptive and flexible, being able to collaborate in teams with people from different disciplines, and (interdisciplinary) knowledge development.

In such types of education, the role of the tutor is changing, from a focus on teacher-oriented teaching towards learner-oriented coaching, facilitating students' knowledge construction. Students are expected to take responsibility for their learning, act independently, and show self-directed behavior [2]. It is often assumed falsely that students have mastered these self-directed skills, but the reality is that they have not. It is, therefore important for tutors to provide enough scaffolding and support [3]. Hardly any research focuses on how teachers in higher education apply this new didactical approach and how it impacts student learning. The primary goal of this exploratory research project is to visualize tutor behavior, and how it is perceived by students to be beneficial for their learning on areas of (interdisciplinary) knowledge development, research abilities and professional skills.

2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Interdisciplinary project-led education

In the third-year semester, students work together in project teams. The pedagogy that is being used has elements from both problem-based and project-led education. A main difference between the two lies in the question whether the product to be delivered is the ultimate goal of the learning trajectory (for example the design of an app, project-led education) or whether the route and knowledge to be gained is central (for example a research paper, problem-based education) [4]. In the semester, students are expected to show and develop research capabilities and professional skills while working on an authentic task from a client. These clients can either be researchers or professionals from industry. Students are also expected to apply and deepen their knowledge. This has reference with problem-based education. At the same time, they are expected to end up with products that adhere to the wishes and needs of the client, conform the focus on products in project-led education [e.g. 3, 5]. The project settings and the challenges in the semester are interdisciplinary. In interdisciplinary project-led education, students use and apply knowledge from two or more disciplines [e.g. 6, 7]. Interdisciplinary challenges do not only require the mere application of knowledge from different disciplines, but also an integrated synthesis of that knowledge. The combination and integration of new knowledge and innovative approaches can evolve, leading to a more adequate and effective solutions to challenges [8].

2.2 Teacher-oriented versus learner-oriented education

The focus of the semester is on the development of self-directed learning skills, knowledge construction, and collaborative learning and working. The tutor is learner-oriented and has a facilitating and a coaching role. Their role is opposite to teacher-oriented behavior, which is characterized by sharing their knowledge through direct instruction, and by a focus on individual learning [9].

The change from teacher-oriented to learner-oriented behavior can be difficult for teachers. In recent research, for example [10], the teaching style of seven tutors working in a problem-based curriculum was studied, focusing on the nature of their interventions, either aimed at content/knowledge or at the process. The researchers distinguished between a directive (teacher-oriented) and supportive (learner-oriented) style (*Table 1*). They also interviewed the tutors, on their beliefs about learner-oriented education. They found that -even when their beliefs matched the underlying assumptions of this type of education- most of the tutors still primarily showed teacher-oriented behavior.

Table 1. Teacher-oriented and learner-oriented interventions [10]

Intervention: Process/ Content	Teaching style: Directive/ Supportive	Category	Teaching Activities
Content	Directive	Teacher-oriented <i>Content Instructor</i>	Transmitting, teaching, informing, explaining, instructing, defining, checking, answering
	Supportive	Learner-oriented <i>Content Activator</i>	Challenging, questioning, activating, motivating, encouraging, exploring, connecting, elaborating
Process	Directive	Teacher-oriented <i>Process Organiser</i>	Directing, structuring, leading, chairing, focusing, inciting, addressing, reassuring
	Supportive	Learner-oriented <i>Process Observer</i>	Observing, evaluating, diagnosing, monitoring, scaffolding, modelling, reflecting

2.3 Tutor competencies

From literature, several competencies can be derived, that are necessary for tutors as coaches in learner-oriented education. These are: modeling, scaffolding, asking the right questions [e.g. 3, 4], monitoring the learning process and formative evaluation of process and product [e.g. 3, 5, 11].

By asking in-depth and supportive questions, tutors activate students' prior knowledge, question their motives and reasoning, elicit students' self-reflection, and support students' self-direct learning (e.g. 11, 12). In addition, it is important that tutors can listen well. An active listening position is desirable, which means that tutors respond verbally or non-verbally to students, summarize what has been said, and have an open, unbiased view during the conversation [13]. In the interaction within a project group, it is also important that tutors show modelling behavior. Tutors set a good example of how to act and interact as a professional [12]. Tutors should also demonstrate empathy, for example through expressing positive expectations and avoiding prejudices, and through encouraging and complimenting students [12].

Tutors should also empathize with the students' thinking and perception world [14]. In addition, a good tutor is able to reflect on his own actions and asks students to provide feedback on his performance. In addition, giving constructive feedback and encouragement increases students' willingness to remain actively involved in the group and the learning process [15]. Finally, tutors can give students scope for their own

learning [14]. They do not dictate students what to do, they try to place the responsibility for choices in the process with the student as much as possible [11].

3 RESEARCH APPROACH

3.1 Context

The context of the research is the interdisciplinary semester in Saxon University of Applied Science, in which currently 22 bachelor programs participate. This Smart Solutions Semester initiated within the faculty of Life Sciences, Engineering and Design (LED), which houses 11 different bachelor programs. Faculty (LED) started the design of the interdisciplinary semester in 2013. Third-year students from three or more disciplines work together in project teams on large (25 ECTS) projects, provided by research groups and business partners. The number of programs participating in the semester is growing, from eleven in September 2018 (750 students and 95 tutors) to 22 programs September 2019. The tasks students work on are complex, authentic, interdisciplinary, and require students to apply a creative and inquisitive approach. Although the type and domain of the projects differ, technology always is a central component. Throughout the 20-week semester, students are supposed to develop their competencies in three areas: professional behavior; application and development of research capabilities; and application and development of knowledge from their own discipline and other disciplines.

The size of a student project team varies from 4-8 students. They are supervised by a tutor. Students work on this project, almost full-time. They meet with their tutor and client regularly, about once a week. In the meantime, students work on their projects wherever they want. They may ask their tutor for support or advice in-between sessions, or they may ask the instructor or another teacher to give a masterclass on a specific subject. Tutors are expected to encourage, question and support students in order to help them grow in these three areas and develop the necessary competences.

3.2 Research questions and data collection

The previous paragraphs show that specific, learner oriented-tutoring behavior, is assumed to be beneficial for student learning. It was also indicated that, in our institution, this type of tutoring behavior is expected from tutors. At the same time, we know from research elsewhere [10] that it is not obvious for every tutor to show this type of behavior. This leads to the question what type of behavior tutors in our organization demonstrate.

Consequently, the following research questions have been formulated:

1. How do tutors shape their tutoring role while coaching students in interdisciplinary project-led education within the Smart Solutions Semester?
2. To what extent do students experience this tutoring behavior as beneficial for their learning?

We broke down this question into several sub questions (*Table 2*). For the purpose of this paper, we focus on answering sub questions 1, 2, 5, and 6. Data has been collected by observing and filming a one-hour tutor meeting with students, of 10 different tutors, within the first 6 till 10 weeks of the semester. From this film, 6 segments were selected, as input for a semi-structured interview fostering reflection with the tutor, and one with the student group. For both interviews, an instrument template was created, containing the same types of questions, so that results from teacher and students could be contrasted.

Data collection was divided between three researchers. The interview sessions were recorded. In the interviews, the observation results were connected to teacher beliefs and students' evaluation and interpretation of the tutor behavior. After the session, the researcher summarized the information in the interview template after which the recording was erased.

Table 2. Overview of research questions and data collection methods

Research questions	Data collection		
	Obs	Interv. Tutor	Interv. Students
1. What behavior do tutors show during a contact moment with a group of students?	X		
2. To what extent can this behavior be labeled as student-oriented or teacher-oriented, according to theory?	X		
3. To which of the three learning areas is this behavior related (e.g. professional behavior, research capabilities, interdisciplinary knowledge and learning)?		X	X
4. How student-oriented or teacher-oriented do students label the tutor behavior?			X
5. What tutor behavior do students experience to be supportive or hindering for their learning?			X
6. What is students' attitude towards student-oriented, interdisciplinary education?			X
7. What is the teacher's attitude towards student-oriented education?		X	
8. How student-oriented or teacher-oriented does the tutor label his own behavior?		X	

3.3 Respondents

The tutors in the Smart Solution Semester are teachers from regular bachelor programs, who have affinity with interdisciplinary education. There is no selection. Most of them have received a small training (3 half-day sessions). Most tutors supervise one or two student groups. They get 4 hours a week per student group (to be spent on student meetings, tutor meetings and intervision, assessment, etc). Ten tutors participated in the study. Since the aim was to explore in general how the tutor role is being shaped, representativeness of respondents was not the main concern in this phase of the study. Therefore, during a tutor training, a general announcement of the research project was made. Six tutors indicated to be available and willing to participate. Four others were deliberately invited since they were regarded by the semester project team to be good tutors.

Condition for joining was the willingness of a few students of their group to participate in the student interview. In total, nine groups were interviewed, 36 students in total. In one case, students did not find time for an interview.

Most of the tutors have a background in science and engineering/technology (*Table 3*). Interviewed students come from the following programs: Applied Physics; Biology and Medical Laboratory Research; Chemical Engineering; Creative Business and Media Information and Communication, Creative Media & Game Technology, Fashion Textile and Technology; Forensic Research, Industrial Product Design; Mechanical Engineering, Nursing, Health & Technology; Entrepreneurship & Retail Management; Software Engineering.

3.4 Criteria for selection of segments

The goal is to get a broad perspective on tutor behavior, the underlying motivation and values for this behavior, on what learning areas tutors focus (interdisciplinary) knowledge development, research abilities and professional skills), and how beneficial this behavior is, according to students. Therefore, we decided to select -per tutor- three segments of supportive behavior and three segments of directive behavior. In both areas, we strove for diversification, by selecting behavior aimed at different learning areas or different types of behavior (such as modelling, questioning, or hints, etc.). This would lead to a broad view of tutor behavior, and the underlying motivation [16].

Table 3: Overview of background of the participating tutors

Background	#
• Biology and Medical Laboratory Research	2
• Chemical engineering	2
• Creative Business - Media, information & Communication	1
• Entrepreneurship & Retail Management	2
• Fashion & Textile Technology	1
• Mechanical engineering	1
• Software Engineering	1

3.5 Data analysis

The analysis was done jointly by the three researchers. First step in the data analysis was to make 2 fact sheets per tutor observation (within-case analysis). One fact sheet contains an overview of the 6 film segments chosen, followed by the researcher's selection criterion (indicating directive or supportive behavior, the tutor reflection, and students' reflection. Also, it was indicated per segment to what extent tutor and students were consistent in their observation and reflection of the tutor behavior.

In the second sheet the tutor interview and students' interview results are summarized and contrasted, on four main themes: 1) vision on the interdisciplinary semester; 2) vision on the tutor role, 3) reflection on the role and value of the tutor sessions in general, and 4) possible needs for further (professional) development or support they have. On this second fact sheet, the researchers finally formulated main conclusions regarding the tutor behavior. The researcher also listed the segments that could serve as good examples of directive and supportive behavior, which could serve as input for professional development activities. These within-case fact sheets were used for further cross-case analyses.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Interdisciplinary education

Students were asked how they experience interdisciplinary work within the Smart Solutions Semester. Six of the nine groups state to find it positive to work together with students from other disciplines, as can be illustrated with this quotation: *"Interdisciplinarity gives a nice view on the projects, a different perspective. Projects in which you work together with several people is positive"*.

Three of the nine groups indicate that they pay attention to and make use of each other's discipline. *"Collaboration is going well. We try to use each other's expertise to arrive at one solution together. It probably makes it easier that we all have a technical background."* Five of the nine groups indicate that they broke down the product to be developed into sub-products, organized mainly around the individual disciplines. These groups state that for them this is the most logical way of working, and they argue

that interdisciplinary work is a challenge due to the limited knowledge of each other's field of study. *“The work is multidisciplinary, which is much more practical. The division of labor is logically linked to the disciplines. There is little contact with the students from the other disciplines of the group, in the context of the project/ assignment”*. Others say: *“the mix between disciplines difficult to integrate, we have not yet learned much about other disciplines.”*

4.2 Student-oriented education

When asked what they think about student-oriented education, most student groups address the degree of freedom (eight of the nine groups).] to make their own choices in the process. Five groups identify this freedom as a positive aspect and indicate that their tutors do provide them ample freedom. However, two of these groups also have reservations, as can be seen from the following quotes: *“We are confident to be self-directed, but stakeholders also give us too much freedom; we actually have no guidelines”* and *“we get freedom, but also lack of clarity and insecurity”*. One group states explicitly that the tutor does want to offer them sufficient freedom, but that the client, on the other hand, directs the assignment. One group of students who does not address the degree of freedom in the answer expresses concerns about the learning efficiency of student-oriented education compared to more traditional education.

4.3 Directive and supportive tutor behavior

In order to get insights into the behaviors of tutors during a contact moment with a group of students, the researchers selected 6 segments per case, 60 in total. Two of these were excluded from the interviews since they reflected the researcher’s general observation of the tutor behavior. Out of the 58 fragments, 25 were labeled as directive, 28 as supportive and 5 as directive/supportive. Table 4 shows how often which behaviors were observed in the selected fragments.

Table 4: Directive and supportive tutor behavior within 58 segments

Directive behavior (25)	Supportive behavior (28)	Directive/supportive (5)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tutor opens the meeting (7) • Questioning the process (5) • Informing about the assessment criteria (portfolio) (4) • Providing suggestions regarding the research approach (3) • Providing suggestions regarding the process (3) • Instructing to use a specific research method (1) • Transmitting content knowledge (1) • Informing about deadlines (1) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Asking questions about the general process (6) • Asking questions about knowledge (5) • Observing (3) • Reflecting with students (3) • Asking questions regarding assignment (3) • Asking questions regarding research (2) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Asking questions about the groups process (2) • Scaffolding (hint) (1) • Encouraging students to take initiative (1) • Reassuring (1) • Monitoring process with respect to deadlines (1) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Directing students to reflect, followed by mirroring students (1) • Asking questions, followed by instruction (1), • Instructing through compelling questions (1) • Asking feedback on behavior and informing about criteria (1) • Through chairing encouraging students to discuss topics (1)

The results from the interviews were connected to the fragments, reflecting to what extent the tutor behaviors are supposed to be supportive for student learning. Out of 58 fragments, 9 were left out (not discussed with students). Out of the remaining 49

segments, in 10 fragments, students find the tutor behavior NOT SUPPORTIVE for their learning (3/21 directive; 5/24 supportive; 2/4 directive/supportive).

For 7/10 segments, this relates to students and tutors having different expectations of the tutor role for the meeting. Tutors intend to have a discussion on content, whereas students only want to inform the tutor about their progress, since they already have their discussions in between tutor sessions. Students expect the tutor to monitor deadlines and support their progress.

For 39/48 segments students find tutor behavior SUPPORTIVE (18/21 directive; 19/24 supportive; 2/4 directive/supportive). For this paper, we chose 8 examples of tutor behavior that both tutor and students find supportive for student learning. We chose an example from the four most frequently selected directive (*Table 5*) and supportive behaviors (*Table 6*).

Table 5. Four segments of directive tutor behavior

1	<p>Opening the meeting T: "Ok, let's get started, with some general stuff. Last week there were concerns about the project. I asked you to write an email with suggestions for improvement. I would like to discuss these with you [=client], to see what we could do. After this meeting I would like to discuss with two students about your personal portfolios and I would like to plan a session on presentations of the portfolio."</p>	
	<p><u>Reflection tutor</u> It was a deliberate choice to take the lead, after the struggles with the client last week. Main goal of the meeting is to get informed by the students.</p>	<p><u>Reflection students</u> This was a supportive action. T. gives good tips and asks questions. T. takes the lead in an empathic way.</p>
2	<p>Questioning the process T: "is there anything else to discuss? How do you work together? Does all go well? No fights?" S: it goes well, there are no conflits S: "it goes fine" S: "not yet". T: "Let's wait and see, probably in the final week, just before the deadline"</p>	
	<p><u>Reflection tutor</u> I find it important to know how they collaborate. In a previous project the group had a conflict which I found out too late</p>	<p><u>Reflection students</u> This action does not bother the students much. They know that their collaboration is fine. It is, however, important that T refers to it.</p>
3	<p>Informing about the assessment criteria T: "I am thinking, let's tell per assessment criterion what seems to you to be a good piece of evidence. And in particular, how do you demonstrate it. What argumentation is relevant, because I think that this is still difficult."</p>	
	<p><u>Reflection tutor</u> S. find working with a portfolio difficult. T. can add value here, by helping them how to collect evidence for the portfolio.</p>	<p><u>Reflection students</u> We find the portfolio difficult. Some elements are difficult to prove. It is nice that T addresses this explicitly.</p>
4	<p>Providing suggestions regarding the research approach T: "My interpretation, actually, is that you work according to design thinking. What your group is doing, is design thinking. This is a method that you can use to make a product."</p>	
	<p><u>Reflection tutor</u> Design thinking is an often used method. T wanted to provide students with insights into where they are in their process and what the next steps are according to this model.</p>	<p><u>Reflection students</u> S find the tutor behavior not at all annoying. Actually very pleasant. It was his observation. Through asking questions and through observations he knows where we stand as a group.</p>

5 DISCUSSION

The research questions guiding this study were: How do tutors shape their tutoring role while coaching students in interdisciplinary project-led education within the Smart Solutions Semester? And to what extent do students experience this tutoring behavior as beneficial for their learning?

5.1 With respect to interdisciplinary project-led education

For the 10 projects in this study, it could be concluded that the type of learning outcomes might be multidisciplinary rather than interdisciplinary in at least half of the cases. This could be due to the fact that the data was collected in the first period of the semester in which students were still starting up. One could argue that there might be a possibility that the nature of the collaboration would change towards more interdisciplinarity during the course of the semester, when students have become

Table 6. Four segments of supportive tutor behavior

1	<p style="text-align: center;">Asking questions about the general process</p> <p>T: <i>“Furthermore, I would like to hear from you what you are all doing and what you are going to do. I don’t want to interfere in that conversation, so I’m just listening to your exchange.”</i> S: <i>“We were actually a bit stuck last week.”</i> T: <i>“Hmhm”</i> S: <i>“We need to select substances and substantiate why we are going to choose that substance. We didn’t get out of this very well. So, we wanted to ask experts from the research group to help organize a focus group.”</i> T: <i>“Oh, how good!”</i></p>	
	<p><u>Reflection tutor</u> T. always asks about the state of affairs, has previously aimed for more exchange between students and now, T. is more listener. T. thinks it is important to know the content of the project.</p>	<p><u>Reflection students</u> S are fine with T asking about it. S see that T. hopes that there will be an exchange between us.</p>
2	<p style="text-align: center;">Asking questions about knowledge</p> <p>T: <i>“Do I understand you’re going to make the substance X with an extra molecule on it or something?”</i> S: <i>“Yes, the idea is to make it with an extra molecule, which is allowed, and if that is done enough we take the molecule off”.</i> S: <i>“And then we have what we need.”</i> T: <i>“So, you end up with a detour to get where you need to be?”</i> S: <i>“Right”</i></p>	

	<p><u>Reflection tutor</u> T. thinks it's fun and important to be up to date on the content as well. T. also believes that S. should be able to communicate about content in layman's terms.</p>	<p><u>Reflection students</u> Very positive; these questions show T's involvement. The question shows that T. knows what is crucial for the project.</p>
3	<p>Reflecting with students</p>	
	<p>[Because of the length of this segment, we provide a summary] In this fragment, students reflect on the contact and the relationship with the client. They state that the client provides contradictory information to students and that, in the opinion of the students, there will be no confirmation from the client. Tutor listens attentively during this segment and asks reflective questions.</p>	
	<p><u>Reflection tutor</u> During a former progress meeting with the client, S. felt overwhelmed by the client T. mentioned this on their behalf and reflected on it with S. Ideally, S. do this themselves, supported by T. But S also need to learn how to have such a conversation, so then an example will help.</p>	<p><u>Reflection students</u> The client was very directive. T stood up for us during the conversation with the client, and reflected on this with us. This was very instructive. Now, we dare to be more explicit to the client.</p>
4	<p>Providing suggestions regarding the assignment</p>	
	<p><i>During this fragment, students are talking to each other in terms of content. Tutor observes during this fragment and does not intervene in the discussion.</i></p>	
	<p><u>Reflection tutor</u> I let students direct from the beginning. Students conduct the conversation and I occasionally mix in.</p>	<p><u>Reflection students</u> We conducted the conversation and T supervised our agreements and structure, so that it does not go in all directions.</p>

acquainted with each other. But given the answers of several respondents, it is more likely to assume that a mere interdisciplinary goal is not being reached yet. One hindering factor might be the choice by management that tutors should only supervise the process, rather than the content. As such, the focus seems to be more on the working process rather than on the underlying learning process. Recent literature shows that in order to reach interdisciplinarity, students should be guided on this learning process [17]. In general, in many education programs the main focus is on process organization (how to get people together, how to communicate), rather than on getting to know each other's discipline. This is supported by the data of these 10 tutors. In order to become really interdisciplinary, it may ask more supervision by tutors in this respect.

Students also differ in the amount of experience with working in project teams when they start the semester. It is a recommendation for the programs to give them that experience earlier in the curriculum. A curriculum structure of moving from multidisciplinary to interdisciplinarity might be useful.

5.2 With respect to tutor behavior

We started the research with the idea that supportive behavior should be preferred above directive behavior. In our study, all tutors showed both directive and supportive behaviors during the tutoring sessions. Strikingly, students are generally satisfied with the tutor behavior, either directive or supportive, and they are not able to identify many explicit points which behavior is counterproductive for their learning process. It could be that there are really no behaviors that are counterproductive to the learning process. However, this is not plausible. It is more likely that students are still insufficiently able to reflect on their own learning process and what is counterproductive in this respect.

Especially when we assume that a number of students are not used to giving shape to their own learning in this way during the first part of their program. The method of data collection may also have had an influence on these results. Although anonymity has been promised in the report, it is possible that students do not dare to be critical of the tutor, who will keep supervising them during the process and who is also an assessor in the semester.

It is thus up to tutors to look for a good balance between the two behaviors, which makes it possible for students to experience a growth in the skills that are central, without the students drowning or swimming. It is important for tutors to make a diagnosis that focuses on where the students stand in their learning process, what their skills are in the area of collaborative and reflective learning, and to what extent they are already self-directed, by, for example, properly assessing the level and needs of the students and, on this basis, making appropriate interventions as a tutor [18].

There might even be a danger in preferring supportive behavior as such to directive behavior. With tutors who are not yet competent in the skills that fit in with student-oriented education, it is possible that students will enter a kind of discovery-learning setting, which researchers have described as ineffective in the past [19]. The tutor then keeps himself on the plane to such an extent that he adds relatively little depth to the learning process that the students are forced to keep on messing around themselves.

5.3 With respect to the research approach chosen

Although it was not object of study, several tutors indicated to value the use of video fragments as a basis for the interviews as a useful vehicle for their own learning process. This was nicely reflected by one of the respondents: *“Those segments are useful. Now, I see things I do wrongly, or things I would like to do in a different way. It is useful to observe yourself. It would be good to do that more often. It is more useful than intervision with colleagues, especially because now you see yourself-in-action. Only from these few fragments, I already see several things that I would like to improve. What I see is that I am sitting in the wrong chair too often, e.g. I am steering the team, rather than letting students steer their process].”*

A nice outcome of this study is that we have 60 segments as examples of specific tutoring behavior. These examples could be used as practical input for a tutor training. Rather than speaking about tutoring, we could show concrete examples to help tutors discuss what are good and weak tutoring behaviors, and to help them reflect on their own behavior as well as their own underlying assumptions. It can build up to a more concrete list of supportive tutor behavior, as an inspiring tool for tutors, or feed the development of HR instruments within the organization.

We suggest, as the next phase in this research project, to select a few successful tutors and film all their sessions during the semester. This will give us more in-depth information about the way the sessions evolve. Whether or not there is a tendency to grow from multidisciplinary to interdisciplinarity, or whether it really depends on the type of assignment. Whether the behavior of the tutor changes over the sessions towards more supportive behavior, since students are becoming more self-directed. In the end, it will yield even more examples that can serve as inspiration and reflection for other tutors.

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